

Zenodo

Research. Shared.

Research Data Management – ISOBIOTICS - Isotopic Labeling of Biotherapeutics

OpenAIRE- Zenodo ISOBIOTICS Community – How to upload guidance

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TIPS BEFORE YOU START THE PROCESS

- We are using the ISOBIOLOGICS ZENODO REPOSITORY, which is officially part of the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo, to showcase and curate all ISOBIOLOGICS Project research outputs in one place, as per the Horizon Europe Program rules and regulations.
- The ISOBIOLOGICS ZENODO REPOSITORY must be used AT FIRST to upload all publications and datasets affiliated with the ISOBIOLOGICS European Project once they have been published in a journal (AND PRIOR ANY UPLOADING ON ANOTHER REPOSITORY PLATFORM).
- After uploading to Zenodo, you may also upload to any other open-access repository, following local rules.
- All PIs are kindly requested to regularly upload and update their respective ISOBIOLOGICS publications in the ISOBIOLOGICS Zenodo Repository.
- You don't have to fill it all in at once.
- Keep clicking the Save button as you add information about your dataset. You can leave the page and return to it. Once you are happy with the information, press Save and then Submit for review.
- Zenodo tutorial - How to use and upload your research YouTube video link - <https://youtu.be/BPVSErzNtME>
- Please, email me at shivani.utekar@cea.fr for any queries or issues regarding the ISOBIOLOGICS Zenodo Repository.

STEP 1 – SIGN IN AND CREATE ACCOUNT ON ZENODO

- Click on the link <https://zenodo.org/>
- Sign in with **OpenAIRE**, **ORCID**, **Email**, or **GitHub** account.

STEP 2 – SELECT THE ISOBOTICS COMMUNITY

zenodo

Select the community where you want to submit your record.

Select a community

Click on Select a community

Type ISOBOTICS

Files

Drag and drop files

Select a community

All My communities

isobiotics

Click on Select

ISOBOTICS - Isotopic Labeling of Biotherapeutics

The ISOBOTICS project is a European interdisci...

Project Owner

« < 1 2 3 4 5 ... 65 > »

STEP 3 – UPLOAD

Drag and drop your data file here or choose file to upload. You then start upload of the file.

Note: this does not upload it in the repository, just on this upload form.

STEP 4 – DESCRIBE

Click on Yes & Copy/Paste the DOI of your original publication

Select the resource type here

Fill in the Title of your dataset

Set the publication date.

Add the creators name and organization affiliation

Write a short description of the dataset here.

Open Access (CC BY) is the default publication license. It means the upload is freely available and usable with the single constraint of crediting/citing/acknowledging the source.

The screenshot shows a 'Basic Information' form with the following fields and annotations:

- Basic Information** (Header, circled in red)
- Digital Object Identifier***: Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes, I already have one No, I need one
- Copy/paste your existing DOI here...**: Input field with a red arrow pointing to it.
- Resource type***: Dropdown menu with a red arrow pointing to it.
- Title***: Input field with a red arrow pointing to it.
- Publication date***: Input field showing '2025-01-27' with a red arrow pointing to it.
- Creator***: '+ Add creator' button with a red arrow pointing to it.
- Description**: Rich text editor with a red arrow pointing to the text area.
- License**: 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International' with a red arrow pointing to it.

STEP 4 – DESCRIBE

You can add contributors with their affiliation, ORCID, Role,

Add the necessary keywords. It helps find uploads and filter them (e.g. by a project).

Add Primary language of your document/upload.

Add date of Submission/Acceptance/Etc.

The screenshot shows a 'Recommended information' form with several sections. A red circle highlights the title 'Recommended information'. Red arrows point from text boxes on the left to specific form elements: one to the 'Contributors' section, one to the 'Keywords and subjects' search field, one to the 'Languages' search field, and one to the 'Add date' button in the 'Dates' section.

Recommended information

Contributors
+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects
Search for a subject by name

Languages
Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD		

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher
Zenodo

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

STEP 4 – DESCRIBE

Funding

Alternate identifiers

Related works

References

Software

Publishing information

Conference

Domain specific fields

Add standard award/grant

isobiotics

ISOBOTICS — Isotopic Labeling of Biotherapeutics 101072780
European Commission

ISOBOTICS: Isotopic Labeling of Biotherapeutics EP/X039501/1
UK Research and Innovation

« < 1 > »

Did not find your award/grant? [Add a custom award/grant.](#)

Cancel Add

Fill in the Funding & Grants Affiliation of the dataset. Type ISOBOTICS and select.

Zenodo allows to list some references. Put the whole reference string.

Add information about the publication;

Fill in the remaining sections of the form with any relevant information where applicable. Complete sections in as much detail as possible.

You can add Metadata info about a conference related to the upload. It is frequent when you upload a poster or conference presentation.

STEP 5 – SAVE AND SUBMIT FOR REVIEW

The screenshot shows a 'Draft' management interface. At the top, it says 'Draft' with an information icon. Below this are two buttons: 'Save draft' (with a lock icon) and 'Preview' (with an eye icon). A prominent blue button labeled 'Submit for review' (with an upward arrow icon) is highlighted by a red arrow from the text box on the right. Below this is a blue 'Share' button (with a share icon). The 'Visibility' section is expanded, showing 'Files only' and two tabs: 'Public' (selected, highlighted in green) and 'Restricted'. Under the 'Public' tab, there is a green padlock icon and the text 'Public' followed by 'The record and files are publicly accessible.' The 'Options' section at the bottom has a checkbox for 'Apply an embargo' (with a clock icon) and the text 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'

Save the uploaded draft and, review it using the preview feature. If you are satisfied, **click on submit for review.**

Once you submit for review, your upload will be reviewed by the ISOBIOTICS Project Coordinator, ISOBIOTICS Project Manager and the ZENODO PM and once it is approved it will be automatically uploaded to the ISOBIOTICS ZENODO community.